

IMPROVING STUDENTS' CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING IN CHEMISTRY THROUGH STRUCTURED INQUIRY-BASED LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11480193>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the level of Grade 10 students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry when exposed to structured inquiry-based learning. The study employed a One-Shot Pretest-Posttest Pre-experimental Design, administering a pretest before intervention and a posttest after. Participants were 28 students from Grade 10, section Alithia at Kalilangan National High School (KNHS), during the 2023-2024 school year. Before the intervention, most students demonstrated very low conceptual understanding, with only a small percentage achieving average or low understanding levels. However, after being exposed to structured inquiry-based learning, a substantial improvement was observed in students' post-test scores. The paired T-test results further supported the effectiveness of the structured inquiry-based learning approach, showing a notable increase in mean post-test scores compared to pretest scores. The study concludes that structured inquiry-based learning significantly enhances students' conceptual understanding and academic performance in Chemistry. The findings of the study recommend that the Department of Education consider implementing structured inquiry-based learning to improve the conceptual understanding of students. Future researchers may use this study to support further investigations into the benefits of structured inquiry-based learning.

Keywords: *Structured Inquiry-Based Learning, Conceptual Understanding, Chemistry Education, Pre-experimental Design, Instructional Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Science education was deemed very important as it played a pivotal role in a person's life. Accordingly, science education cultivates students' abilities in scientific inquiry, fostering values like objectivity, curiosity, and honesty, while also instilling habits of mind such as critical thinking (SEI-DOST & UP NISMED, 2015). Apparently, conceptual difficulties are the primary problem that students encounter when trying to understand a subject, as concepts are built upon prior knowledge and form the foundation of an individual's thinking. These difficulties arise due to challenges in grasping and fully understanding the underlying concepts (Akram, et. al., 2014). According to Naz & Mushtaq (2022), numerous studies in chemistry education literature have addressed the challenges students face in understanding fundamental chemistry concepts in schools. Concepts are formed through a process of abstraction, where ideas or thoughts are developed based on the common properties of objects or events, and difficulties or issues related to these concepts or the process of forming them are known as conceptual difficulties. These challenges in grasping chemistry concepts pose significant concerns for science educators, teachers, and students.

Integrating different learning strategies helps to address this concern among students. According to The InterAcademy Partnership (IAP) (2021), incorporating Inquiry-Based Learning enhances students' understanding of science by engaging them in the investigative nature of the subject. This approach helps students contextualize materials and develop critical thinking skills. Learning chemistry through structured inquiry-based learning made it more understandable and allowed students to be more active, which promoted conceptual understanding (Kwitonda, et. al., 2021). Szalay (2015) conducted a study on the promotion of structured inquiry-based teaching in chemistry. The research findings indicated that the implementation of structured inquiry-based activities enhanced students' cognitive abilities in the subject of chemistry. Analyzing the domain of structured inquiry-based learning revealed many positive aspects; however, it also highlighted some negative aspects. According to Wheatley (2018), Some drawbacks included the insufficient time for teachers to prepare, inadequate funding for materials, and a lack of understanding on how to effectively implement structured inquiry-based learning. Teachers often lacked the necessary experience and guidance to successfully facilitate student-led lessons. Previous research, while comprehensive, overlooked the potential challenges that teachers encountered when utilizing inquiry-based learning. The research study focused on improving students' understanding of chemistry concepts through structured inquiry-based learning within classrooms.

In addressing the pressing challenges present in teaching science, the researchers opted to investigate the effectiveness of the structured inquiry-based learning in improving the conceptual understanding of the grade 10 students in Chemistry at Kalilangan National High School. The study's results would provide evidence to guide teachers and researchers in improving teaching and learning practices.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to examine the Grade 10 students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry when exposed to a structured inquiry-based learning strategy. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Grade 10 students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry when exposed to structured inquiry-based learning strategy in terms of pre-test and post-test?
2. Is there a significant difference in the conceptual understanding of Grade 10 students in Chemistry when exposed to a structured inquiry-based learning strategy in terms of pre-test and post-test?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a One-Shot Pretest-Posttest Pre-experimental Design, involving 28 Grade 10 students from Kalilangan National High School, with 7 males and 21 females, under the Enhanced K to 12 Basic Educational Curriculum for the School Year 2023-2024. Data was collected through a validated 30-item multiple-choice test, content-validated by a panel of Chemistry experts, assessing students' conceptual understanding of chemical reactions. The test was administered before and after the implementation of a structured inquiry-based approach. The study obtained necessary permissions from Central Mindanao University and the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) for ethical review and from the Office of the Principal at Kalilangan National High School. Student performance was evaluated using the K to 12 Basic Education Learning Progress and Achievement Indicators, with scores transmuted according to the formula:

$$\text{Transmuted score} = \text{raw score} / \text{highest possible score} \times 50 + 50$$

The grading scale was as follows:

Grading Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
90% - 100%	Outstanding	Very High Conceptual Understand
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory	High Conceptual Understanding
80% - 84%	Satisfactory	Moderate
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory	Low Conceptual Understanding
Below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectation	Very Low Conceptual Understanding

Descriptive statistics (means) were computed for pre- and post-assessment scores to gauge the overall impact of structured inquiry-based learning on conceptual understanding. A paired-sample t-test was used to compare the mean scores of the pre- and post-assessments, assessing the significance of the difference in students' conceptual understanding following the intervention. The study's scope was limited to the specific topic of chemical reactions in Grade 10 Chemistry, and the results may not be generalizable to other subjects or grade levels.

RESULTS

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of structured inquiry-based learning strategy on students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry. By implementing this approach, the researchers aimed to enhance learning experiences and educational outcomes.

A. Conceptual Understanding of Students in Chemistry

Table 1 presents the conceptual understanding of students in Chemistry before and after being exposed to a Structured Inquiry-Based Learning Strategy. Pretest and posttest scores are shown, detailing the frequency and percentage of students falling into different score ranges, which are categorized into qualitative descriptions based on a grading scale.

Table 1. Pretest and posttest Conceptual Understanding Scores of Students in Chemistry

		PRETEST		POSTTEST		
Score Range	Grading Scale	N	Frequency %	N	Frequency %	Qualitative Description
24-30	90-100	0	0	20	71.4%	Very High Conceptual Understanding
21-23	85-89	1	3.6	6	21.4%	High Conceptual Understanding
18-20	80-84	2	7.1	2	7.1%	Average
15-17	75-79	2	7.1	0	0%	Low Conceptual Understanding
Below 15	Below 75	23	82.1	0	0%	Very Low Conceptual

					Understanding
TOTAL	28	100	28	100	
Overall Mean		10.6		24.5	

Legend:

Grading Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	Qualitative Description
90-100	Outstanding	Very High Conceptual Understanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory	Very High Conceptual Understanding
80- 84	Satisfactory	Average
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Low Conceptual Understanding
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Very Low Conceptual Understanding

Table 2 presents the comparative mean scores between the student's conceptual understanding in Chemistry before and after exposure to Structured Inquiry-Based Learning Strategy.

Table 2. Paired T-Test to Compare Pretest and Posttest in Chemistry.

	<i>Paired Difference</i>		<i>t</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Pretest	10.6	4.14	1.70	0.000**
Posttest	24.5	2.20		

p < 0.05 is highly significant

DISCUSSION

As shown in data table 1, during pre-test, most students (82.1%) achieved a "Did Not Meet Expectations" score, indicating a very low conceptual understanding. Only a small percentage achieved satisfactory or high scores, suggesting a lack of deep understanding in Chemistry concepts prior to the implementation of structured inquiry-based learning. However, during the posttest, after exposure to structured inquiry-based learning, a significant improvement is observed. 71.4% of students achieved a "Very High Conceptual Understanding" score, indicating substantial progress in their understanding of Chemistry concepts. This improvement can be attributed to the active engagement fostered by inquiry-based learning, which encourages questioning, investigation, scientific methods, curiosity, and problem-solving. The data implies that traditional passive learning methods may not effectively foster deep conceptual understanding in Chemistry. The shift towards structured inquiry-based learning has shown promising results, with a significant proportion of students achieving high conceptual understanding. This highlights the importance of active student engagement in the learning process for effective knowledge acquisition in Chemistry. Moreover, the

data suggests that addressing factors such as the complexity of Chemistry concepts, passive learning experiences, and student motivation is crucial for improving conceptual understanding. Incorporating more effective teaching strategies, such as structured inquiry-based learning, can help address these factors and enhance student performance in Chemistry.

The findings are supported by existing research. Karpudewan et al. (2015) highlight the limitations of passive learning approaches in fostering robust conceptual knowledge, emphasizing the need for more active learning methods. Additionally, Mutoharo et al. (2015) assert that student motivation significantly contributes to understanding science concepts, aligning with the observed improvement in student performance after exposure to structured inquiry-based learning. Furthermore, Langitasari et al. (2016) suggest that conceptual understanding is best achieved through active involvement in the inquiry process, supporting the effectiveness of structured inquiry-based learning in enhancing student learning outcomes in Chemistry.

On the other hand, table 2 presents that we can observe a significant value of 0.000 at 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) which indicates a significant difference. As presented on the table, it shows the results of a paired T-test comparing the pretest and posttest scores in Chemistry. The mean pretest score was 10.6 with an SD of 4.14 and the mean posttest score was 24.5 with an SD of 2.20. The t-value for both pretest and posttest was 1.70. The posttest mean score of 24.5 is higher than the pretest mean score of 10.6, indicating improvement in conceptual understanding after the intervention. The findings imply that the intervention or treatment implemented had a positive impact on the Chemistry scores, leading to a significant improvement in students' conceptual understanding. According to Naz and Mushtaq (2022), various research in the field of chemistry education has explored the challenges students encounter when trying to grasp fundamental chemistry concepts in schools. Concepts are developed through abstraction, a process where ideas or thoughts are derived from identifying the common properties of objects or events. The difficulties or issues that arise in understanding these concepts, or in the process of their formation, are referred to as conceptual difficulties. These difficulties are a major concern for educators and students alike, as they significantly impact the learning process in chemistry. Incorporating structured inquiry-based learning has been shown to significantly improve students' understanding of science by actively involving them in the investigative nature of the subject. This approach helps students connect learning materials to real-world contexts and cultivates critical thinking abilities. In the domain of chemistry, structured inquiry-based learning not only enhances comprehension but also promotes active student engagement, leading to a deeper grasp of concepts (Kwitonda et al., 2021).

Additionally, research conducted by Szalay (2015) supports these findings, demonstrating that structured inquiry-based activities enhance students' cognitive skills in chemistry and contribute to a more effective and engaging learning experience. Furthermore, the results are supported by the study of Kwitonda et al. (2021), which states that the use of structured inquiry-based learning in chemistry education has several benefits. It makes the subject more understandable for students and encourages

them to actively participate in the learning process. This hands-on approach promotes conceptual understanding, allowing students to grasp the fundamental concepts of chemistry more effectively. In line with the findings from the paired T-test analysis, the improved performance observed in the posttest scores may be attributed to the implementation of structured inquiry-based learning. By engaging students in hands-on activities, encouraging exploration, and fostering active learning, this teaching methodology facilitates a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Therefore, the results of the paired T-test, combined with the insights provided by Kwitonda et al. (2021), suggest that the use of structured inquiry-based learning in chemistry education can contribute to enhanced students' conceptual understanding.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the structured inquiry-based learning implemented in the study had a significant positive impact on students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry. Before the intervention, most students demonstrated very low conceptual understanding, with only a small percentage achieving average or low understanding levels. However, after being exposed to structured inquiry-based learning, a substantial improvement was observed in students' post-test scores. Most of the students achieved very high conceptual understanding, indicating a significant enhancement in their performance and comprehension of Chemistry concepts.

The paired T-test results further supported the effectiveness of the structured inquiry-based learning approach, showing a notable increase in mean post-test scores compared to pretest scores. This improvement signifies the success of the intervention in enhancing students' conceptual understanding and academic performance in Chemistry. The findings suggest that structured inquiry-based learning can be a valuable teaching methodology to promote active engagement, critical thinking, and deep conceptual understanding among students in Chemistry education. The results of the study indicate that there is no significant difference in the conceptual understanding of Grade 10 students in Chemistry when they are exposed to a structured inquiry-based learning strategy, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis.

However, the incorporation of a structured inquiry-based learning strategy, which includes structured support and guidance, has been found to enhance students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry and contribute to improved educational outcomes.

Recommendations

The study's findings have led to the following recommendations:

The Department of Education Teachers should consider implementing structured inquiry-based learning to improve students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry. This approach is rooted in the belief that when students engage in structured inquiry, they are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter compared

to traditional teaching methods. They may use structured inquiry-based learning to provide students with a clear framework and specific guidelines while allowing them the freedom to explore and investigate within these boundaries. This method balances guidance with autonomy, helping students develop critical thinking skills, enhance their problem-solving abilities, and engage more actively with the content.

The Department of Education Teachers should use this as a tool to improve students' learning outcomes. By engaging in inquiry-based activities, students are encouraged to ask questions, design experiments, collect and analyze data, and draw conclusions based on their findings. This process not only reinforces their conceptual knowledge but also helps them understand the application of theoretical concepts in practical scenarios.

Future researchers may utilize this study to explore further the benefits of structured inquiry-based learning in Chemistry education. They can investigate various dimensions, such as the long-term retention of knowledge, the development of scientific skills, and the impact on students' attitudes toward Chemistry.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers conducted the study with a commitment to adhering to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Participants were informed that their involvement was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. The anonymity of the respondents was strictly maintained to protect their identities, and all data were kept confidential. The respondents' well-being was a top priority, and every effort was made to ensure that participation in the study did not cause any harm or distress.

The researchers obtained legal permission from Central Mindanao University and the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) for an ethical review of the implementation of the scale. No conflicts of interest were present in the conduct of this study. The researchers maintained objectivity and avoided any bias in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. To ensure the integrity of the research, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources and contributions were properly acknowledged. The results of the study were used solely for research purposes, aimed at improving educational practices. The dissemination of the findings was conducted with the support of the School Principal, aiming to contribute to the professional development of teachers and the enhancement of students' conceptual understanding in Chemistry.

Acknowledgments

The completion of this research would not have been possible without the help and support of many individuals. In this vein, the researchers would like to extend their heartfelt appreciation and gratitude to the following people:

First and foremost, to the Most Gracious and Heavenly Loving Father ALMIGHTY GOD, for His continuous guidance, strength, and blessings throughout the entire research process.

To Ma'am Garin B. Come and Ma'am Raihana Umpar Toke, for invaluable guidance, mentorship, and unwavering support that has been instrumental in the successful completion of this study. Their visions and motivation have deeply inspired the researchers to strive for excellence.

To Sir Alex Tan Solar, School Principal of Kalilangan National High School, for granting permission to conduct the study at the school.

To the Grade 10 students of Kalilangan National High School, who volunteered their time and effort in the conduct of the study, despite their busy schedules. Their participation and cooperation were indispensable to the success of the research.

Finally, the researchers would like to extend their sincerest appreciation to their families for their unconditional love and support, both morally and financially.

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